

Abolition of Slavery

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Introduction

Practiced since ancient times, slavery was exercised on the vanquished in general, members of another clan, ethnic group or country, or of another religion. In ancient times, men of the people conquered were massacred; women and children were taken into slavery. Closer to home, in Africa and the Middle East, women slaves were more valuable because they were used as concubines and worked the land (Horton, pp 16). Some slaves were soldiers, wives, tutors, mentors, managers, officials, sometimes of very high rank, with a very considerable power. In 1865, by end of the Civil War, the United States marked the abolition of slavery throughout the country.

Description and Analysis

In America, slavery has taken new forms. Its development is closely linked to that of agricultural labor on large scale commercial plantations. Initially, it was Europeans that we took into forced labor to work the land owners need to arm settlers were institutionalized such that the "contract labor" of Europe by bringing workers destitute who should give four to seven years of plantation life in exchange for payment of their travel to the New World (McKivigan, pp 90). A contract even more popular with farmers and owners of the South that the state granted them an additional 80 hectares of land per worker imported! This contract laborer was totally subservient to his master under identical conditions to slavery: corporal punishment was common, the wedding band, they could be sold for the remainder of the contract, escapes or disobedience punished by an extension of the contract and sometimes red-hot iron, etc.

When American slavery is a new and terrible

It was in 1619 that the twenty first African slaves landed in Virginia. Initially, their fate was variable: they slept, ate, worked under contract with the Europeans, sometimes intermarried

with them, and were released for a third of them. But in the late seventeenth century, the need for hands to work the land in the South tripled while contract workers from Europe are scarce from the year 1660. Farmers are turning to Africa, to bring this time not at all voluntarily and massively, workers who serve for life and even less that could be saved only their own color denounced them. Slavery then took on this continent, in agricultural areas, a totally new, both for their work on the racial aspect of the operation. From the 1680s, an arsenal of laws completely separated the white population of the black, rising steadily. The first code of slavery was established in Virginia, in 1680 and in South Carolina, in 1690.

10 to 11,000,000 Africans deported

An estimated 10 to 11 million Africans deported as slaves in America. Only a minority (600 000-650 000) was bound for North America, leaving the other to Brazil and the Caribbean. But as the living and working there were extremely harsh, that there used often as men, they did little strain. It is the minority sent in North America that gave birth to the largest slave population of the Americas (since a child of slaves was necessarily slave). In 1810 for example, said the expert Peter Kochlin, were found in the U.S. 1.1 million slaves, doubling of all Africans "imported" into this region in 200 year".

Conclusion

During the Civil War, Northern states did not agree on anything (or the rights of workers, women or customs duties) ... except one thing: they all agreed to abolish the slavery. It was officially abolished on 1 January, 1863, by President Lincoln, but it was not until the end of the war and victory for the North was voted in January 1865, the Thirteenth Amendment to the Constitution prohibiting slavery throughout the floor of the United States of America. There was a fundamental, immediate legal change, but that racism was slow to make it effective in social

relations.

References

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